

Review

Development of HBV Model and its application in Asian High Mountain Basins

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Abstract: The snow accumulation and its melting in high mountain basins are highly affected by climate change due to which the hydrological modeling is being more important to understand the regime. Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansavdelning (HBV), is a hydrological model for daily runoff simulation, particularly applied in high mountain basin, which is enormously popular with many researchers. That is why, this review article attempts to express a brief overview of the HBV model applications and feasibility in Asian high mountain basins. Overall, the research supported that the model simulation with its calibration and validation process carried out with the measured discharge which ultimately believed to be helpful in reducing the errors. In addition, the review has concluded that improving model structure, the calibration process, model equation and, satellite or radar-based precipitation data as a complement to station gauge could significantly improve general runoff simulation and prediction. Thus, HBV model seems to be in a great shape for Asian high mountain basins with minor additional adjustment. Likewise, the sources of error in the runoff simulation are the indistinctness causing inaccuracy in the meteorological forecasts. Further work is essential to understand why some catchments display a similar behavior by sharing good parameter sets to HBV model.

Keywords: HBV model, high mountain basin, runoff simulation

1. Introduction

The different characteristics of watershed and climate are the main drivers of the hydrological changes which may cause the major consequences related to environmental destructions

(Kundzewicz and Robson, 2004). At the same time we cannot ignore that the earth surface has been getting warmer every year resulting in melt of snow and ice (Rangwala and Miller, 2012), which quickly responds to slight variation in temperature (Carrivick and Brewer, 2004). The mountain region are more sensitive than other land surfaces of same latitude (Beniston et al., 1997; Rangwala and Miller, 2012) is facing greater magnitude of global warming causing environmental changes around the world (Singh et al., 2011). Furthermore, the water originated from the mountainous region due to glacial melt (Stoffel et al., 2016) and variation in precipitation (Campbell et al., 2011; Kure et al., 2013) are highly vulnerable to environment which may later cause the fluctuation in streamflow causing either floods or droughts (Reggiani and Weerts, 2008). The snow transitions to glacier ice causing drastic shifts in overall runoff although the continued shrinking would increase the seasonality of runoff impacting irrigation and hydropower and alter the hazards (Bolch et al., 2012). Also, the high mountain basins are characterized by steep channel gradient with sources of water from glacier melt, and rainfall increasing the flow velocity (Weingartner et al., 2003). Due to the steepness, the mountain rivers have higher flow velocity and run through a narrow gorge and straight valley which can be the measures to determine the hydrological changes in the streamflow (Wyzga, 1993). Therefore, the development in hydrological modeling has led us to the advancement of the spatial and temporal resolution, accuracy, and the lead time of forecasts for all principal hydrological variates. Hydrological modeling deals with the simulation, where simulation is the imitation of any operation of real world system over time (Banks et al., 2001). So, simulation can be used as a technique to investigate the detail dynamic of a hydrological system, to perform numerical experiments (Hartmann, 1996).

The lack of hydrological stations in the high altitude always shortens the data availability and creates inaccuracy in modeling. This will ultimately cause an improper representation on the regime during the simulation. The simulation remains far from perfect, however, there are a vast sources of additional information which yields potential benefits, that the hydrological simulation or forecast could bring to our society (Krzysztofowicz, 2001). It is required to determine the inflow and other necessities for the appropriate flood design and a systematic approach to assess overall risk profile for its management (Clavet-Gaumont et al., 2017).

There are many Rainfall-Runoff model to transform the precipitation to runoff, which ranks from black box i.e. simple system method (e.g. Unit hydrograph, regression, transformation model etc.) to conceptual model (Crawford, tank, Snowmelt runoff model (SRM), HEC models

etc.) and then to more rigorous i.e. distributed models (e.g. Système Hydrologique Européen (SHE) Model, Institute of Hydrology Distributed Model (IHDM)) and semi distributed models (e.g. TOPMODEL, Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT), HBV). Despite having many Rainfall-Runoff model, Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansavdelning (HBV) is widely used in high mountain basin. Hence, this review mainly introduces HBV model from its applications. For this, the past literatures based on development of HBV model and its application in the Asian high mountain basins were reviewed.

2. Overview of HBV model

a. HBV model

The HBV is a conceptual, precipitation–runoff, semi–distributed model for daily runoff simulation originally developed by the Swedish hydrologist Sten Bergstrom of Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (Bergstrom, 1976, 1995). The model is available in different versions such as HBV-96, HBV light, HBV-SED, HVB-N and, HBV ETH which varies in complexity and utility features according to the required parameters (Aghakouchak and Habib, 2010; Arheimer and Bergström, 1999; Bergström, 1992; Braun and Renner, 1992; Harlin, 1991; Klose et al., 2013; Lindström et al., 1997; Seibert, 1996). Further, the HBV model was re-evaluated to improve the potential for the spatially distributed data resulting in the new version of HBV-96. It led to some changes in process description for snow accumulation and melt, evapotranspiration, ground water discharge, and automatic calibration as shown in Figure 1. Later, the modifications of the parameters (e.g., threshold value of temperature, water equivalent of snow) were combined to give significant improvement in the model performance. After the use of Automatic Weather Station (AWS) to measure the precipitation and temperature, the automatic calibration scheme was developed to improve the model efficiency (Lindström et al., 1997). The HBV-96 model was used in different catchments of Europe, America and Africa using the Monte Carlo techniques (Khu and Werner, 2003; Vrugt et al., 2008) for the calibration and parameter analysis where it was found that the components of water balance has a significant influence on the model performance (Lidén and Harlin, 2000). Therefore, a new user-friendly version was developed, naming HBV light, to simulate the discharge where the catchment can be divided into twenty elevations and three vegetation zones. Thereafter each divided elevations into three different ordinate classes among north, south and east/west were later used for elevation mapping which will further help in model development (Seibert, 1996). For the hydrological processes and their uncertainties, as a

compliment of the hydrological features, a modeling toolbox, HBV ensemble was presented. It includes MATLAB graphical user interface and an ensemble simulation that can be used for uncertainty analysis, parameter estimation and model sensitivity (Aghakouchak and Habib, 2010; AghaKouchak et al., 2013).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of HBV model (Seibert, 2005)

The HBV model has the advantage of minimum input data requirement. So, HBV-ETH variant was developed for rainfall-runoff simulation in the alpine catchment with emphasized snowmelt algorithm (Klose et al., 2013). The model includes conceptual numerical descriptions of the hydrological processes at the catchment scale (Bergström, 1992). The general water balance is described as given in the Equation 1.

$$P - E - Q = \frac{d(SP+SM+UZ+LZ+Lakes)}{dt} \quad (1)$$

Where, **P** = precipitation; **E** = evapotranspiration; **Q** = runoff; **SP**= snow pack; **SM** = soil moisture; **UZ** = upper ground water zone; **LZ** = lower ground water zone; **Lakes** = lake volume.

It was used in numerous countries (Table 1) with varying climatic and topographical conditions for flood prediction, forecasting and water resource assessment. It was also used in the estimation of nutrients together with covering real-time forecasting, gap filling with data quality control, an extension of runoff records and, flood modeling as well as synoptic water balance analysis and, climate change impact on runoff (Bergström, 1992; Jia and Sun, 2012; Jutman, 1992; Krysanova and Müller-Wohlfeil, 1997; Primožič et al., 2008).

Nonetheless, with the help of such a model, the scientific assumptions seem to be one of the major insights into the key hydrological processes and, possibly, potential hydrological consequences of climate change.

The variables associated with the hydrological forecasting are divided into different parameters (e.g., threshold temperature, snow fall correction factor, water equivalent of snow, refreezing coefficient, percolation rate, linear outflows, MAXBAS, threshold value) under snow routine, soil routine, response routine, and routing routine. Here, the routine and routing respectively stands for the process of model simulation in various inbuilt physical processing stage with an input for the simulation parameters such as precipitation, temperature and evapotranspiration (Bergstrom, 1976; Lindström et al., 1997; Seibert, 1996). The observed precipitation and temperature data from meteorological station and recorded discharge from the hydrological station along with the potential evapotranspiration, based on Penman method (Penman, 1948) are used as a primary data in the model. The information of the topographical features along with the direction and speed of the wind makes the model more accurate (Johansson, 2002). As the altitude increases, the evapotranspiration may increase or decreases, causing errors in the simulation.

A correction of evapotranspiration using temperature gradient with altitude was introduced for the accuracy of the model (Lindström et al., 1997). A threshold temperature around 0°C is set where the precipitation is assumed to be rain for rise air temperature and snow for fall in air temperature. Similarly, the study by Primožič et al., (2008) also highlighted the temperature is an important parameter in case of the snow routine, whereas altitude gradient is used for its altitude correction.

Table 1. Overview of application of HBV model

Region	Model	Purpose	Reference
Alpine karst basin, Swiss Alps	HBV-ETH	Discharge simulation	(Hottelet et al., 1993)
Langtang river basin, Nepal	HBV3-ETH	Discharge simulation	(Braun et al., 1993)
Heihe river, China	HBV	Runoff response simulation	(Kang et al., 1999)
Solvenia	HBV-96	Flash flood forecasting	(Kobold and Brilly, 2006)
Ala Archa, Abramov (Kazakhstan), Oigaing (Uzbekistan)	HBV-ETH	Hydrological response to climate change	(Hagg et al., 2007)
Sava river basin (Croatia)	HBV	Discharge simulation	(Primožič et al., 2008)
Sora river basin, Slovenia	HBV	Flash flood	(Grillakis et al., 2010)
Tamor basin, Nepal	HBV	Discharge simulation	(Normand et al., 2010)
Likhu river basin, Nepal	HBV	Hydrological study	(Shrestha and Alfredsen, 2012)
Ferghana valley, Central Asia	HBV light	Simulation of water resources availability	(Radchenko et al., 2014)
Langtang, Nepal	HBV light	Climate change scenario	(Adhikari et al., 2014)
Karnali River basin, Nepal	HBV light	Hydrological study & Climate change impact	(Shiwakoti, 2017)
Narayani River basin, Nepal	HBV light	Climate change impact	(Bhattarai et al., 2018)

b. Model performance evaluation

The evaluation of model performance is based on precipitation, temperature and discharge time series data of a long historical period, which play a crucial role in calibration and validation of the model. Validation is applied with the parameter sets focusing on high and low flows along with the parameter sets from the GAP optimization for evaluation (Normand et al., 2010). Since, validation is highly influenced by the runoff variability, the river basins should be carefully examined for the isolated precipitation events (Bhattarai et al., 2018). Whereas, the regular data sets can be used in the model for simulation without any interruption to acquire discharge but in case of irregularity in time series data an interpolation is required for the precipitation input to avoid a systematic underestimation or overestimation of runoff during the simulation of the model. The overall precipitation correction factor must be a fixed value (e.g., 1.1 for Langtang, Nepal by Braun et al., (1993); for a catchment), if the catchment has minimum or even no discharge records. The parameters for the model can be estimated using regional information such as topography, elevation and, snow cover if the catchment with similar characteristics and can be used as the model parameter. The regionalization should not focus on relating individual parameters to the catchment properties but on relating them to compatible parameter sets or vectors (Bárdossy, 2007). A process-oriented calibration scheme where initial parameter estimates were made from recession analysis of observed runoff. The parameters were calibrated individually in an iteration loop starting with snow routine which yielded a good model performance after a manual calibration (Harlin, 1991). Seibert et al. (2000) studied in a nested basin of Germany (Dreisam, Bmgsa, Talbach), where the model was calibrated individually for all the three basins using optimized parameter values related to size and other properties (e.g., degree-day factor, snowfall correction factor) and were validated by using the runoff series of the remaining two basins (Bmgsa, Talbach). In second step, model was calibrated with the runoff series from all three basin with model efficiency of 0.8 (Seibert et al., 2000). Selecting longer periods of temporal variability in hydrological analysis, simulation for water balance analysis is demonstrated by the chosen values of Nash Sutcliffe, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and high flow ratio given with longer temporal variability (Rusli et al., 2015). The spatial and temporal differences may cause an alteration in parameter change. Additionally, snow and ice respond by melting to slight variations

in temperature, which causes uncertainty and errors during the simulation. Hence, the increasing temperature will result in wet flow regime as mentioned in Shiwakoti (2017). Furthermore, there is a significant challenge in communicating uncertainty information, if they are not properly understood they could create confusion or disturb the evaluation process. Therefore, model performance is directly based upon reliable and valid time series data. Some studies with their model evaluation are presented in Table 2 with NSE- Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency and R^2 - Coefficient of determination.

Table 2. Model evaluation used for HBV model

Region	Model evaluation	Reference
Slovenia	(NSE = 0.8)	(Kobold and Brilly, 2006)
Germany	(NSE = 0.84)	(Bárdossy, 2007)
Ala Archa, Abramov (Kazakhstan), Oigaing (Uzbekistan)	(NSE = 0.88,0.89, 0.83)	(Hagg et al., 2007)
Sava river basin (Croatia)	($R^2 = 0.8$)	(Primožič et al., 2008)
Sora river basin, Slovenia	($R^2 = 0.9$) and (NSE = 0.8)	(Grillakis et al., 2010)
Tamor basin, Nepal	($R^2 = 0.6$) and (NSE = 0.6)	(Normand et al., 2010)
Likhu river basin, Nepal	($R^2 = 0.8$)	(Shrestha and Alfredsen, 2012)
Narayani River basin, Nepal	($R^2 = 0.6-0.8$) and (NSE = 0.5-0.8)	(Bhattarai et al., 2018)

c. Handling of model simulation error

The handling of errors during the simulation of HBV model highly depends upon the hydrological catchments and its characteristics. The uncertainty in a HBV model generally propagates from an atmospheric model (Seibert, 1997). Some of the inaccuracy of climate model prediction are emission scene, glacier and snowmelt, scale degradation technique, and the physical process parameter, neglecting which causes impact on the surface runoff (Nan et al., 2011). Also, the types of precipitation (e.g. rain, snow, and sleet) project a great impact on surface runoff and energy balance however, many weather stations only record raw precipitation data overlooking the information about type of precipitation (Ding et al., 2014) ultimately leading to the inaccuracy in the model prediction. The other sources of error in the runoff simulation are the ambiguity of observed runoff used in model calibration and inaccuracy of the meteorological forecasts (Hostache et al., 2011).

For the improvement of the results, it is very important to work with excellent runoff data and improved meteorological forecasts (Khanal et al., 2014). Monte Carlo method is generally used to quantify the uncertainty of the model parameters (Khu and Werner, 2003; Vrugt et al., 2008). An extension of the alert system to combine weather parameters and conditional probabilities has shown potential in narrowing decision criteria (Kok et al., 2011), which, on further development can include probabilistic surge and river level forecast reducing the level of uncertainty (Kok et al., 2011). There is a significant challenge in communicating uncertainty information, if they are not properly understood they could create confusion or dilute the evaluation process. At this time, sensitivity studies will provide a first assessment of the most critical parameters of the model. For example, more measurements of selected variables such as snow-water equivalent and glacier mass balance are required to gain confidence in modeled discharge and the intermediate results of model snow storage and ice melt (Braun et al., 1993).

There is a greater responsibility for modeling to present uncertainty estimates along with a model prediction (Pender and Néelz, 2007). The possibility of compensation between parameter and hydrological change detection work is considered necessary to figure out the parameters that specifically represent the watershed characteristics and how the soil and the vegetation degradation relate to change in parameter values at large scale (Gebrehiwot et al., 2013). Hence, the spatial

differences when searching for temporal differences in parameter changes should be accounted (Gebrehiwot et al., 2013). It could encourage users to reject parameterizations that correctly represent runoff but with incoherent internal variables (Ambroise et al., 1995; Franks et al., 1998). Modifications of model equations can also help to reduce the uncertainty of the parameters (Gupta and Sorooshian, 1983).

3. Discussion

The study on Karst basin of the Swiss Alps defined the implementation of an operationally used HBV ETH model where three additional parameters were added, for aspect-dependent snow melt, and controlling the water losses associated with the karst (Hottelet et al., 1993). The values for parameters were obtained externally, through a manual procedure for discharge-based calibration (Hottelet et al., 1993). Therefore, apart from the standard hydrometeorological network, simple conceptual model is recommended.

Similarly, Braun et al., (1993) modified the HBV ETH model and simulated elevation dependent snow accumulation and glacier mass balance as well as daily discharge in 38 per cent glacierized basin of Langtang Khola, Nepal. The study has declared a reduction factor (0.5) of glacier melt within the debris-covered parts and identified the region to be dominated by snow and glaciers which are sensitive to the pattern of daily discharge (Braun et al., 1993).

In addition, HBV-ETH model has been used in five glacierized catchments in Central Asia, of Tianshan mountain with successful simulation performance in the continental climate (Hagg et al., 2007). Only 50 percent current glacier extent was considered to predict future runoff scenarios. In contrast, temperature and precipitation changes were performed simultaneously in separate model run, where glaciation was reduced for the comparable scenarios.

To assess the future changes in water availability, Renner and Braun., (1990) applied the HBV ETH model. Its use in the upper Panj catchment, of the Amu-Darya rivers reveals deglaciation of 36 and 45 % respectively during the rise of temperature between 2.2 to 3.1 °C. The model was further modified for the regional climate scenarios and the resulting glacier changes. The circumstances of runoff show only a small decline in the annual runoff as the diminishing glacier

region is almost balanced by higher melt levels. For example, the seasonal change in water supplies from summer to spring is having a negative impact on agriculture and irrigation in the lowlands (Hagg et al., 2013). The study on the hydrological contribution in cold regions has grown over the years, where meltwater play a key role in river runoff and estimated in the global scale (Schaner et al., 2012). The underestimation of the peak flow in the Tianshan Mountains was the major error, likely caused by inadequate simulation of heavy rainfall in summer (Aizen et al., 2000) and extreme precipitation events (Jasper et al., 2002).

Moreover, with the use of the modified HBV- D model, Wang et al. (2019) has tried to enhance temperature index model with high resolution and seems to be advantageous over the degree day method since melt is ignored in original HBV- D and SWAT – glacier the degree day based hydrological model can be influenced. Normand et al., (2010), in Tamor river basin HBV model showed some difficulties due to the topographic structure for the high and low flows at different outlets in the sub-basins. Yet, HBV correctly simulated the low flows except for some sharp peak flows, mainly due to isolated precipitation. Therefore, two sets of parameters were prepared for the low and high flows for the high performance of the model. Genetic Algorithm Package (GAP) optimization was applied for the calibration and was manually calibrated to refine the parameters by trial and error. For the validation of the model, the parameter sets with the focus on high flows and low flows, are set from the GPA optimization for comparison. Additional data would support the process for enhancing the simulation result (Normand et al., 2010; Seibert, 1996, 1997). Adhikari et al., (2014) implemented downscaled results from temperature and precipitation, which accurately simulated the regular discharge data at the Langtang Khola outlet at Syaprubesi hydrological station (2002–2004). During the summer and spring, the model usually expected a rise in precipitation and a decline during the winter and fall seasons. The average estimated discharge will increase for all seasons except spring, relative to a minimum estimated summer discharge (Adhikari et al., 2014).

An empirical sediment model HBV-SED was developed by Lidén et al., (2001) and applied in the Odzi river of Zimbabwe to simulate riverine fine sediments transport. Their model assessed the nitrogen transfer by using HBV-N modeling in Sweden (Arheimer and Bergström, 1999). It can

work as a useful tool for effective planning and regulation of water resources projects (Hottelet et al., 1993).

In the review by Arheimer et al. (2011) on the identification of sensitivities in Swedish flood forecasting system, it concluded that the general runoff simulation and prediction could be significantly improved by model structure and calibration, equations, and new precipitation input using radar data as a complement to station gauge. MODIS-based study in Swiss Alps found uncertainty in snow cover maps (Finger et al., 2015) and glacier mass balance (Huss et al., 2010) of around 10% which were featured for all the datasets. These datasets yielded ten best parameters for the calibration of the HBV-light model. So, in the basin with low degree of glacierization the representation of the snow cover is decisive, hence, the runoff projection is not correct; which is crucial in the field of the hydropower. Overall, multi-dataset calibration approaches are used to improve the realism of the hydrological process in the impact assessment and to support the decision making for new hydropower structures (Etter et al., 2017) .

The model had to be uniquely adjusted for each basin and, while tuning model parameters, it was very useful to compare simulated and calculated glacier mass balance values in the heavily glaciated basin. The importance of this model is based in the fact that it can generate accurate simulations of discharges of basins located in various physiographical regions and for stationary conditions (Braun and Renner, 1992). As remotely sensed estimates of the mass balance become more reliable and wider available, the value of glacier mass balance data for selecting parameters for runoff simulations are encouraging. The drainage system and the complex internal storage of large glacier surfaces result in variations between simulated runoff and observed runoff (Xu et al., 2017). To constrain hydrological models, future research should evaluate the value of remotely sensed glacier mass balance data (Konz and Seibert, 2010).

The main advantage of HBV model is that their structure is more physically based, and that they are less demanding on input data than the fully distributed models. Also, the spatial resolution in HBV model is accounted by using probability distributions of input parameters across the basin. Our finding shows that physical model parameters are usually very unclear and should be treated with sound uncertainty. It is also important to use information from comprehensive post-event

surveys with HBV modeling, which will minimize variability in estimating peak discharge and understanding hydrological events.

The review showed that an interpretation of changes in detection can be unreliable with only parameters. Also, the modeling change identification should require comparisons of simulations using the various parameter sets to see the overall changes in the simulated hydrological system, and not just evaluating changes in the value of individual parameters. The problem should be examined to what extent this depends on the model and also to what extent on the catchment property (Bárdossy, 2007). If the ranges of parameter values are to be further limited for a given set of basin characteristics, then the model must be extended to a greater number of basins. Here, an automated optimization procedure as stated by Harlin (1991) based on current parameter sensitivity awareness could permit more fruitful investigations (Braun and Renner, 1992). However, the outcomes also show that parameter values cannot be directly related to the basin characteristics. This supports the findings of Bergström (1991) that physical definitions of model parameters are usually very ambiguous and should be treated with sound skepticism. It is important to use a combination of information from extensive post-event surveys with rainfall-runoff modeling, which will reduce the uncertainty in estimating peak discharge and understanding events. Consequently, the principle of parsimony in rainfall runoff modeling can be extended to a low computational demand-efficient flash flood warning system for the study area, when combined with active radar casts now or high-resolution weather forecast models (Grillakis et al., 2010).

4. Conclusion

This review presents the application of HBV model in hydrological studies for a river basin by analyzing the features of the runoff in Asian high mountain basin. The HBV model parameters can be classified based on flows and the whole basin can be divided into sub-basins according to the elevation, vegetation, and land use. It is found that by improving model structure, calibration, model equation, and new precipitation data from radar as complement to station gauge, general runoff simulation and prediction could be drastically improved. Indeed, in the application of the HBV model, the simulated runoff data are reliable. However, to improve discharge simulations in future, peak flow simulation requires additional effort with a more complex model. It highlights the fact that modeling choice and statistical methods can have important effects on outcome. The

necessity of further research to improve the performance of the HBV model in simulating extreme runoff events in data-scarce mountain areas are required.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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